

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BIFACIAL HALF-CUT PERC MONOCRYSTALLINE PV MODULES UNDER OUTDOOR CONDITIONS IN NAWABSHAH CITY

Muhammad Moosa Jakhrani¹, Abdul Sattar Saand², Faheem Ahmed Solangi^{*3},
Muhammad Ishaque⁴, Zuhebullah Soomro⁵, Faisal Zardari⁶

^{1,2,4}Electrical Engineering Department, Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology, Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan

^{*3,6}Mechanical Engineering Department, Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology, Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan

⁵Electrical Engineering Department, the University of Larkano

^{*3}faheemahmed@quest.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15635053>

Keywords

Solar radiation, ambient temperature, wind speed, humidity, bifacial half-cut photovoltaic module performance analysis

Article History

Received on 31 April 2025

Accepted on 31 May 2025

Published on 10 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Faheem Ahmed Solangi

Abstract

Electrical characteristics of both front and rearside of bifacial photovoltaic modules are normally examined at standard test conditions and rarely at outdoor environments. This work was carried out to inspect the electrical properties (front and rearside) of bifacial half-cut PERC mono-crystalline photovoltaic modules in Nawabshah city's opened environment. This study measured the PV module's power output (P), open-circuit voltage (Voc), short-circuit current (Isc), maximum voltages (Vmax), maximum current (Imax). Weather parameters included global solar radiation (Ir), ambient temperature (Ta), wind speed (Ws), and relative humidity (Rh). A light meter (HD-2302) was used to measure the amount of global solar radiation that struck the site's horizontal surface, while PROVA AVM-05 was used to record the ambient temperature (Ta), wind speed (Ws), and relative humidity (Rh). Also via the PV analyzer PROVA-1101, the electrical properties of the PV modules both (front and rear) sides were recorded from 09:00 to 16:00 hours at an interval of 15-minutes. The average Ir, Ta, Ws and Rh were found 842.4W/m², 29.7°C, 3.0m/sec and 46.0% respectively during study period. The PV module's average Pmax, including both the front and back sides, was 334.6W, with the rearside alone producing 27.6W. It is established from the study that the front side produced around 91% of output power and the rest is contributed by its back-side during analysis period at the same operational and environmental conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Energy is backbone of economic growth and sustainable development through the fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas could be one way or can be obtained from hydro, solar, wind, biomass, geothermal or other alternative sources [1]. Nevertheless the primary source of greenhouse gases

and the ultimate driver of global warming is fossil fuels. On the other hand, as a result of global population growth and industrial advancements, energy demand is progressively increasing. The nations are concentrating on raising the proportion of renewable resources in the overall energy demand

in order to effectively address this scenario. It was expected that system might be expanded to 1220 GWs for using renewable energy resources through 2024[2,3]. Besides the solar energy systems technologies are more reliable, environmental friendly, reliable as well as sustainable than other renewable energy sources. One way to produce electrical energy is by Photovoltaic or solar thermal systems. The photovoltaic system is simpler way to generate electrical energy as compare to solar thermal systems also the Photovoltaic systems are very easy to maintain and provide consumers with direct electricity. Solar photovoltaic technologies are more preferred [4, 5]. However, the amount of solar radiations that the solar modules receive directly affects their performance, and mounting techniques, W_s , T_a , and R_h also have an indirect impact [6-8]. Pakistan is one of the world's most populous and developing nations. To continue developing and to address the issue of energy safety, it needs a steady supply of energy. The nation is currently experiencing a severe energy crisis, with 10 to 12 hours of darkness per day [4,5]. There is electricity shortfall in Pakistan is about to 51,765 GWh [9, 10]. Thankfully, Pakistan receives a lot of sunlight, It is a desirable alternative for delivering power to remote areas where it is challenging to extend transmission lines from the national grid [11].

PV modules electrical characteristics are evaluated under STC are maintained at covered environment by keeping the PV modules planetary solar radiations at $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, temperature at 25°C , as well as the air mass of 1.5 by the manufacturers [12, 13]. The marketable efficiency of PV modules like polycrystalline, mono-crystalline and amorphous are 12-13%, 14-15% and 6-7% at STC[14]. Their power output can also be decreased by various operational conditions, weather parameters, and geographical conditions [12,15,16]. The electrical properties of PV modules are negatively impacted by ambient temperature by 0.2% to 0.5%/°C above the nominal cell operating temperature [17, 18]. Additionally with advanced technology Passivated Emitter Rear Cells (PERC) were produced in place of silicon based technologies by PV industries which are expected to account for 45-60% of the market by 2027 [20, 21]. According to the passivation layers deposited, PERC technology has a reported efficiency of about 22%

[22]. Additionally, it has been reported that bifacial PV modules can increase system efficiency (5-25%) compared to monofacial counterparts. Author's [22, 23-27], reported that their actual contribution is still questionable due to influence of geographical, environmental and operational parameters and its configuration. It is still unknown that, how much percentage of power output can be obtained from the backside of bifacial modules at a particular location. Although, these modules are proved to be more beneficial at snowy conditions yet their performance in hottest environments is to be ascertained [28, 29], Even through hypothetical the Bifacial modules having more advantages in snowy conditions, little is known about how well they work and what their backside energy gain is high in hot environmental and outdoor conditions. Additionally the efficiency of PV modules was predicted using various empirical efficiency models. The reason for this investigation is the erratic nature of environmental factors that may affect the electrical properties of PV modules and adjust their performance. The purpose of this research work is to investigate the electrical properties of half-cut bifacial PERC monocrystalline PV modules' front and rear sides in outdoor environmental settings. Additionally, it aims to determine the bifacial modules' rear side energy gain in relation to their front side. Furthermore, the study explores the suitability of existing models for accurately forecasting the performance of such modules under these environmental conditions. In order to determine the power output of the rear side of the bifacial module in comparison to the front side, this study was carried out in Nawabshah city, to examine the electrical properties (front and back) of bifacial half-cut PERC modules in one of Pakistan's hottest location [30].

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two PERC half-cut monocrystalline bifacial photovoltaic modules were used in this research investigation, compass, metal stand and structure for measuring the weather parameters, the light meter and weather station were utilized, For assessing electrical characteristics of photovoltaic modules, The both modules were acquired with the same

specifications, and their attributes were evaluated as stated in Table 1.

The system was installed over the Energy Systems Engineering’s departmental buildings at QUEST, Nawabshah, and orientation towards true south at a 26° slope angle horizontal. One module was covered from the front and opened from the rear side to examine its rear side performance, while another PV module was left open on both sides to view its combined electrical characteristics. Using a professional weather station (HP-2000), weather parameters like I_r (W/m^2), T_a ($^{\circ}C$), W_s (m/sec), and R_h (%) were measured as shown in Figure 1. The PV Analyzer (PROVA-1011) was used to measure the electrical characteristics of each PV module, specifically the V_{oc} , I_{sc} , V_{max} , I_{max} , and P_{max}

output. PV modules were connected to the computers and data loggers in order to store and analyze the data.

2.1 Photovoltaic modules

Both monocrystalline bifacial modules were of same specifications employed for determining their electrical characteristics and power output by keeping these at various environmental and operational conditions as given in Table 1. The rated power of both bifacial modules was 545W at standard test conditions (STC). When the modules are rated at solar radiation of $1000W/m^2$, ambient temperature (T_a) of $25^{\circ}C$ and air mass of 1.5 m/s are referred to as STC. In addition to the two bifacial modules.

Selected PV Module technologies: Monocrystalline Bifacial Half-Cut		
Manufacturer		JA SOLAR
Model	--	JAM72530-545/MR
Open circuit voltages (Voc)	V	49.60
Short circuit current (Isc)	A	13.86
Rated Voltages (Vmax)	V	41.64
Rated Current (Imax)	A	12.97
Rated Power (Pmax)	W	545
Open circuit voltage tolerance	%	±2
Short circuit current tolerance	%	±4
Power production tolerance	%	±3
Testing condition	STC	STC
PV module area	m²	

Table. 1. Electrical features of PV Modules

2.2 Experimental setup

Compass was used to place the photovoltaic modules at the required slope and orientation. It shows the direction of any location with respect to true north. The angles markings in degrees shown on the compass, as north corresponds to zero, east 90, south 180, and west 270 degree. These degrees can be used to affix the module at the desired orientation and slope. The materials used for metal stand were metal rods, screws, frame, bars, nuts and bolts etc. The metal stand was made by welding and jointing the pieces of sheets and rods in the Mechanical

Engineering Workshop. The every reading was taken between 9:00 and 16:00 Pakistan Standard Time, with a 15-minute break in between the data collection.

2.3 Electrical characteristics of bifacial modules at outdoor conditions

In this section, methodology for electrical characteristics, namely, V_{oc} , I_{sc} , V_{max} , I_{max} and P_{max} output of total (front + rear side) versus only rear side of bifacial module was discussed. The coefficient

of correlation for data set of both modules was determined.

Least square method was adopted for best fit model to determine how different parameters relate to the data that was observed. A variety of models, including polynomial, Fourier, Gaussian, power, exponential, sum of sine, and other custom functions, were tested using the MATLAB curve fitting toolbox. On the basis of goodness of fit, the best possible model was selected for prediction of power output of modules.

Data of front and rear side (total) of one module and only rear side of the other module was taken by fixing the modules at same level above the ground surface. Rear side of both modules was being made open for incoming diffuse (reflected) radiation. Front side of the other module was being covered by a wooden material to block the direct radiation hitting the surface of the module. The modules are fixed at optimum tilt angle (slope) with that of location latitude as shown in Figure 1. Finally, the contribution of rear side with respect to total power output of bifacial module was determined.

Figure 1. Electrical characteristics of bifacial solar photovoltaic modules: uncovered front and rear sides and covered front side or uncovered rear side

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Calibration of photovoltaic modules

Two bifacial photovoltaic modules were purchased with similar specifications and then installed and studied for performance analysis at outdoor conditions. Although, these both modules were rated at standard test conditions by the manufacturers, yet for verification and validation, their electrical characteristics (P_{max} , I_{max} , V_{max} , V_{oc} and I_{sc}) are investigated at real outdoor conditions. The analysis

of one module, PV-1 and other module PV-2 was carried out to calibrate their electrical characteristics with each other and find out their percentage error before fixing out PV-1 without any adjustment and other module PV-2 with changes in operational parameters. PV-1 gave average power of 185W and PV-2 184W during calibration period. PV-1 gave 0.8% more power output than PV-2 as shown in Figure 2.

In general, the percentage error was found less than one percent, thus was considered negligible and ignored during subsequent analysis. The error between both modules was quite less in early and late hours of the day and slightly more during midday.

However, overall percentage error between both examined modules is less than one percent, which was considered as negligible and overlooked in upcoming parameter evaluations.

Figure 2: Percentage error between bifacial photovoltaic modules

3. Power output of bifacial modules at outdoor conditions

This section includes the results of power output of total (front + rear side) of one module versus only rear side of other bifacial module, their correlation between each other and percentage change in their average maximum power output. A time-dependent model for the bifacial module's power output along

with determination of percentage error between the fitted model and observed data is given.

3.1. Weather parameters during the analysis of bifacial photovoltaic modules

The hourly average measured weather parameters like G_{rad} (W/m^2), T_a ($^{\circ}C$), R_h (%), W_s (m/sec) and T_c ($^{\circ}C$) are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Weather parameters during analysis of bifacial photovoltaic modules

The maximum values of G_{rad} , T_a , R_h , W_s and T_c were noted $996W/m^2$, $37.68^\circ C$, 59.88% , $4.47m/sec$ and $67.46^\circ C$ during the analysis of bifacial photovoltaic modules with monofacial photovoltaic module. Whereas, the minimum values were recorded $422.38W/m^2$, $30.45^\circ C$, 36.84% , $3.0m/sec$ and $49.39^\circ C$. Moreover, the average weather parameters like G_{rad} , T_a , R_h , W

3.2. Bifacial PV modules' Open circuit voltages and Short circuit currents (front and rear sides) in comparison to the rear side

The hourly average measured open circuit voltages and short circuit current of examined modules are presented in Figure 4. The maximum, minimum and average values of open circuit voltages (V_{oc}) of bifacial PV module (front and rear side) were recorded 44.9 , 44.4 and $44.8V$, and rear side bifacial module produced 44.9 , 41.4 and $41.8V$.

Figure 4: Comparing the short circuit current (Isc) and open circuit voltage (Voc) of the front and rear side Bifacial PV modules to the rear side Bifacial PV module

Whereas, the maximum, minimum and average short circuit current (I_{sc}) of bifacial PV module (front plus back side) was recorded 12.5, 7.6 and 10.9A, and rear side bifacial PV module generates 1.5, 1.2 and 1.4A respectively. It was noted from results that bifacial PV module (front and rear side) gave 3V (7%) and 9.5A (87.15 %) more average V_{oc} and I_{sc} than rear side bifacial PV module. It is clear that rear side bifacial PV module produced approximately 12% short circuit current during analysis period.

3.3. Maximum voltages and current of Bifacial PV Modules

The hourly average maximum voltages (V_{max}) and maximum current (I_{max}) of examined PV modules are

display in Figure 5. The maximum, minimum and average values of voltages of bifacial PV module (front and rear side) were recorded 41.0, 36.3 and 37.6V, and rear side bifacial module produced 36.4, 34.5 and 35.2V.

Whereas, the maximum, minimum and average current of bifacial PV module (front plus back side) was recorded 10.5, 6.5 and 8.9A, and rear side bifacial PV module generates 0.87, 0.65 and 0.79A respectively. It was noted from results that bifacial PV module (front and rear side) gave 2.4V and 8.11A more V_{max} and I_{max} than rear side bifacial PV module. It is clear that rear side bifacial PV module produced approximately 0.79A maximum current during examined time.

Figure 5: Maximum voltage (V_{max}) and current (I_{max}) of Bifacial PV modules (front and rear side) versus Bifacial PV module (rear side)

3.4. Power output of total (front + rear side) versus only rear side of bifacial module

The correlation between the average maximum powers of one bifacial module (both front plus rear side) against other bifacial module (rear side only) with respect to time was found 0.9880. It was observed that the values of coefficient of correlation between these were very close to each other. The comparison of average maximum power output of bifacial module front plus rear side and rear side only are illustrated in Figure 6. It is found that

minimum average power output from the both front plus rear side of bifacial module was around 240 W at 1600 hours and maximum average at 1300 hours with 380W. The trend for rear side of module regarding average power out was same as that of both front plus rear side. However, the rear side of the bifacial module gave an average power output of around 30W. It is discovered from the analysis that as solar radiation was increasing the average power out of the modules was increasing and vice versa. The contribution of the bifacial module's rear side

was found directly proportional to the front plus rear side of the module. It means that during noon hours share was found increasing due to higher availability of solar radiation.

The percentage change in the average maximum power output of front plus rear side versus rear side only of bifacial module are shown in Figure 7. Average minimum percentage change of average maximum power output from both front plus rear side versus rear side only with respect to time was

noted in early (at 0900) and late hours (at 1600) of the day with around change of 10%, while small change was noted during noon with approximately 7%. The rear side gave 8.5% power of total (front plus rear) side of bifacial module. It is discovered that rear side of the module might perform better during higher solar radiation and temperature periods (around noon) compared to morning and evening.

Figure 6. Comparison of maximum power output of bifacial module front side plus rear side versus rear side with respect to time

Figure 7. Percentage change in the maximum power output of bifacial module when the front plus rear side versus rear side

3.5. Time dependent model of power output of bifacial module with its front plus rear versus rear side

Curve fitted power output model of bifacial module with its total (front plus rear sides) versus rear side

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\max_{bcr}}(P_{\max_{bfr}}) = & -6.481 \times 10^8 + 8.631 \times 10^8 \cos(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) \\
 & 4.188 \times 10^7 \sin(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) - \\
 & 2.15 \times 10^8 \cos(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) - \\
 & 2.092 \times 10^7 \sin(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}})
 \end{aligned}$$

(1)

Equation (1) is a fitted model, which shows the relationship between the maximum power outputs of front plus rear side versus rear side only. This is a Fourier type nonlinear model. Its goodness of fit parameters, like SSE were noted as 0.6593, R-square 0.987, Adjusted R-square 0.9544 and RMSE 0.5742. When comparing the developed curve fitted models of the bifacial module with the observed data in Figure 9 which shows that the percentage error between the total (front plus rear side) to rear side. It was discovered that the percentage error was less than ± 1.5%, which is actually very small. At midday, the average maximum error was recorded at ±1.5, but

only is shown in Figure 8. A time dependent curve fitted model for bifacial modules with respect to its total (front plus rear sides) against rear side only is given in Equation 1.

in the early hours of the day, the error was negligible at ≤0.5.

The ratio function between the bifacial modules' front and rear power outputs is displayed in Equation (2). The antecedent in the ratio function is the number that is being divided, and the consequent is the term that is being divided. This function can be used for comparison purposes and provides information about the amount of time that one quantity is equal to another. The ratio is the number that can be used to express one quantity as a fraction of another. It should be mentioned that two numbers in a ratio can only be compared if they have the same unit.

$$\frac{P_{\max_{bcr}}}{P_{\max_{bfr}}} = \frac{\left(\begin{aligned} & -6.481 \times 10^8 + 8.631 \times 10^8 \cos(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) \\ & 4.188 \times 10^7 \sin(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) - \\ & 2.15 \times 10^8 \cos(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) - \\ & 2.092 \times 10^7 \sin(0.0001581 P_{\max_{bfr}}) \end{aligned} \right)}{P_{\max_{bfr}}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 8. Curve fitting model for maximum power outputs of front plus rear side versus rear side

Figure 9. Percentage error between the developed model and its total versus rear side power output with the observed data

4. CONCLUSIONS

5. Both selected bifacial photovoltaic modules studied were calibrated with each other by verifying their electrical characteristics using error analysis and found less than one percentage error. The

contribution of rear side of bifacial module in the early hours of the day was 10% and around noon 7% of the total (front plus rear side). It is discovered that rear side of the module might perform better during lower solar radiation and temperature periods

(around noon) compared midday. Whereas, the time dependent model for of bifacial module with its total against rear side power output was a Fourier type nonlinear model and displayed overall percentage error of ± 1.5 and less than 0.5 percentage in the early hours of the day.

The average I_r , T_a , R_h , W_s and module temperature were found 842.4W/m^2 , 29.7°C , 46.0% and 3.1m/sec and 54°C respectively during study period. In contrary to the weather parameters, the average V_{oc} of PV module (front plus back side) was 44.8V and only backside 41.8V . It is noted that V_{oc} was not profoundly affected by the amount of I_r . The average I_{sc} of PV module (front plus back side) was noted as 10.9A and only backside was 1.4A . The I_{sc} was decreased by 87.6% . Thus, there was loss of I_{sc} as well as power. Only the rearside of the PV module produced 27.6W , while the average maximum power output (P_{max}) of the front and rear sides was 334.6W . It should be noted that the module's rear side power output only accounted for 8.25% of the total power generated. The study's findings, which are consistent with previous findings published by other researchers, indicate that the rearside of the bifacial module contributes only about 9% of the total power produced by the bifacial PERC photovoltaic module in outdoor conditions in Nawabshah city.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and Technology (QUEST) Nawabshah, Pakistan, is acknowledged by the authors for providing the facilities for this research work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jakhrani AQ, Othman AK, Rigit ARH, Samo SR. Assessment of solar and wind energy resources at five typical locations in Sarawak. *Journal of Energy and Environment* 2013; 4(1); 1-6. <https://journal.uniten.edu.my/index.php/jee/article/view/120>.
- [2] Karabulut M, Kusetogullari H, Kivrak S. Outdoor performance assessment of new and old photovoltaic panel technologies using a designed multi-photovoltaic panel power measurement system. *International Journal of Photoenergy* 2020; Article ID 8866412; 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8866412>.
- [3] IEA, Renewables 2019, IEA, Paris, 2019, March 2020 <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-2019>.
- [4] Jatoi AR, Samo SR, Jakhrani AQ. Influence of temperature on electrical characteristics of different photovoltaic module technologies. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development* 2018; 7(2); 85-91. <https://doi.org/10.14710/ijred.7.2.85-91>.
- [5] JakhraniAQ, Othman AK, RigitAR, SamoSR, KambohSA. Estimation of incident solar radiation on tilted surface by different empirical models. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications* 2012; 2(12); 1-6. www.ijsrp.org.
- [6] JakhraniAQ, OthmanAK, RigitARH, Samo S.R. Determination and comparison of different photovoltaic module temperature models for Kuching, Sarawak. In *Clean Energy and Technology (CET), 1st IEEE First Conference* 2011; 231-236. DOI: 10.1109/CET.2011.6041469
- [7] Jatoi AR, Samo SR, Jakhrani AQ. An improved empirical model for estimation of temperature effect on performance of photovoltaic modules. *International Journal of Photoenergy* 2019; Article ID 1681353; 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1681353>.
- [8] BarykinaE, Hammer A. Modeling of photovoltaic module temperature using Faiman model: sensitivity analysis for different climates. *Solar Energy* 2017; 146; 401-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.03.002>.
- [9] NTDC, 2018. *Power System Statistics*, 43rd Edition. NTDC, Lahore, Pakistan.

- [10] Yaqoob H, Teoh YH, Din ZU, Sabah NU, Jamil MA, Mujtaba MA, Abid A. The potential of sustainable biogas production from biomass waste for power generation in Pakistan. *Journal of cleaner production* 2021; 307; 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127250>.
- [11] Adnan S, Khan AH, Haider S, Mahmood R. Solar energy potential in Pakistan. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 2012; 4(3); 032701. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4712051>
- [12] Jakhrani AQ, Samo SR, Kamboh SA, Labadin J, Rigit ARH. (2014). An improved mathematical model for computing power output of solar photovoltaic modules. *International Journal of Photoenergy* 2014; Article ID 346704; 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/346704>.
- [13] Skoplaki E, Palyvos JA. On the temperature dependence of photovoltaic module electrical performance: a review of efficiency/power correlations. *Solar energy* 2009; 83(5); 614-624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2008.10.008>.
- [14] Kalogirou SA. *Solar energy engineering: processes and systems*, Amsterdam: Academic Press: Elsevier, 2014.
- [15] Duffie JA, Beckman WA. *Solar engineering of thermal processes*, Fourth Edition, New York: Wiley, 2013.
- [16] Jatoi AR, Samo SR, Jakhrani AQ. Performance evaluation of various photovoltaic module technologies at Nawabshah Pakistan. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development* 2021, 10(1); 97-103. <https://doi.org/10.14710/ijred.2021.32352>.
- [17] Evelyov V, Rodgers P, Bojanampati S. Enhancement of photovoltaic solar module performance for power generation in the Middle East. In *Semiconductor Thermal Measurement and Management Symposium (SEMI-THERM)*, 28th Annual IEEE; 87-97; 2012. DOI: 10.1109/STHERM.2012.6188831
- [18] Abdulgafar SA, Omar OS, Yousif KM. Improving the efficiency of polycrystalline solar panel via water immersion method. *International Journal Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology* 2014; 3; 83-89. www.ijirset.com.
- [19] Dullweber T, Schmidt J. Industrial silicon solar cells applying the passivated emitter and rear cell (PERC) concept-A review. *IEEE journal of photovoltaics* 2016; 6(5); 1366-1381. DOI: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2016.2571627.
- [20] Dullweber T, Schulte-Huxel H, Blankemeyer S, Hannebauer H, Schimanke S, Baumann U, et al. Present status and future perspectives of bifacial PERC+ solar cells and modules. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics* 2018; 57; 08RA01; DOI 10.7567/JJAP.57.08RA01
- [21] Siddiqui A, Bektaş G, Nasser H, Turan R, Usman M. Impact of ion implantation and annealing parameters on bifacial PERC and PERT solar cell performance. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* 2022; 53(2); 102583; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102583>
- [22] Ghosh S, Yadav R. Future of photovoltaic technologies: A comprehensive review. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* 2021; 47; 101410; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101410>
- [23] Congedo PM, Malvoni M, Mele M, De Giorgi MG. Performance measurements of monocrystalline silicon PV modules in South-eastern Italy. *Energy Conversion and Management* 2013; 68; 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2012.12.017>.
- [24] Dida M, Boughali S, Bechki D, Bouguettaia H. Experimental investigation of a passive cooling system for photovoltaic modules efficiency improvement in hot and arid regions. *Energy Conversion and Management* 2021; 243; 114328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114328>.

- [25] Gao Y, Ji J, Cui Q, Dai Z, Chen B, Wang C et al. Experimental study on performance assessment of photovoltaic/thermal-thermoelectric generator systems: Bifacial and tandem types. *Energy Conversion and Management* 2023; 295; 117591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117591>.
- [26] Deline C, MacAlpine S, Marion B, Toor F, Asgharzadeh A, Stein JS. Assessment of bifacial photovoltaic module power rating methodologies-inside and out. *IEEE Journal of photovoltaics* 2017; 7(2); 575-580. DOI: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2017.2650565.
- [27] Lu W. Power generation characteristics of bifacial photovoltaic modules under different backgrounds. In 2021 IEEE international conference on artificial intelligence and computer applications (ICAICA) 2021; 470-473. DOI: 10.1109/ICAICA52286.2021.9498001.
- [28] Baldus-Jeursen C, Petsuik AL, Rheault SA, Pelland S, Côté A, Poissant Y, Pearce JM. Snow losses for photovoltaic systems: Validating the Marion and Townsend Models. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics* 2023; 610-620; DOI: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2023.3264644.
- [29] Tao Y, Bai J, Pachauri RK, Wang Y, Li J, Attaher HK. Parameterizing mismatch loss in bifacial photovoltaic modules with global deployment: A comprehensive study. *Applied Energy* 2021; 303; 1-17; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117636>.
- [30] M. M. Jakhrani, A. S. Saand, A. Q. Jakhrani, A. R. Jatoi, and K. C. Mukwana, "Electrical Characteristics of Half-Cut Bifacial PERC Monocrystalline Photovoltaic Modules under Outdoor Conditions in Nawabshah," *J. Hunan Univ. Nat. Sci.*, vol. 51, no. 5, 2024.

